

Resorption in Endodontics III

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External cervical resorption(ECR)

ECR usually occurs in the cervical region of the tooth immediately below the epithelial attachment. It has the potential to invade the root dentine in any direction and to varying extent. In advanced cases, ECR can progress into the mid- and apical thirds of the root.

Aetiology and prevalence

The precise aetiology of ECR is poorly understood. Studies have shown that ECR could be multifactorial, with orthodontic treatment being the most commonly associated factor. Other factors frequently implicated are the history of trauma, parafunctional habits, poor oral hygiene, periodontal treatment etc. Orthodontic treatment and history of previous dental trauma or existing parafunctional habits are frequently seen combined in cases of ECR. Other factors that have been reported to contribute to ECR include extraction of adjacent teeth, herpes zoster virus infection, feline viruses, playing wind instruments, the use of bisphosphonates and intracoronary bleaching. All the suggested aetiological factors are considered predisposing factors or association rather than causative, to date, there is no evidence of the cause-and-effect relationship.

The pathogenesis of ECR is not fully understood. Damage to the protective unmineralized cementum allows the odontoclastic cells to resorb the underlying dentine.

Clinical features

There is no 'classic' presentation of ECR. The clinical findings can be variable depending on the severity and nature of the resorptive defect, tooth type and stage of ECR. It is often asymptomatic in the early

stage. Occasionally, a 'pink spot' may develop in the cervical region of the tooth, and it can be detected as an incidental finding if it occurs at the labial/buccal or lingual/palatal surface. The pink discoloration is due to the fibrovascular granulation tissue occupying the resorptive cavity, giving the tooth a pinkish hue, through the thinned overlying enamel and dentine. Loss of periodontal attachment and profuse bleeding due to disturbing the vascular granulation tissue upon probing of the resorptive defect are among the other clinical features of ECR. Moreover, probing of ECR defects often gives a hard and scratchy tactile sensation, which helps to differentiate it from caries. In advanced cases, the resorption may eventually perforate the root canal wall and enter the pulp. Subsequent bacterial contamination of the pulp may result in symptoms and/or signs of pulpitis and/or periapical periodontitis. The affected tooth/teeth usually respond to pulp sensitivity tests, except if the ECR has perforated the pulp chamber and pulp necrosis has ensued.

Radiographic features

ECR can have varying radiographic features depending on the location, severity and phase of the lesion, i.e. resorptive or reparative. ECR often presents as a radiolucency in the resorptive phase; however, in moderate to advanced cases, the lesion may have mottled radiographic appearance as the body attempts to repair the resorptive defect. The border of the resorptive defect may be well defined or have a ragged, irregular appearance. There is no 'classical' radiographic appearance of ECR. The root canal outline is visible as long as there is no perforation of the root canal wall. It can be difficult to distinguish ECR from IRR especially when the tooth is asymptomatic.

Management

Management of ECR depends on the nature and accessibility of the lesion. Treatment aims include excavation of the resorptive lesion to arrest the resorptive process, restore the resorptive defect and monitor the affected tooth for recurrence. Prevention of ECR is not predictable as the cause of ECR is unknown. The treatment options of ECR include external repair with(out) root canal treatment (RCT), internal repair along with RCT, intentional replantation (IR), periodic review with sensitivity testing or extraction for untreatable ECR.

External repair involves surgical exposure of the resorptive defect, complete excavation of the defect and restoration of the defects with composite, glass ionomer cement or Biodentine. RCT is indicated in the cases with (near) perforation of the root canal by ECR, and/or there are signs/symptoms of irreversible pulpitis, pulp necrosis or apical periodontitis. The root canal should first be accessed before external repair, a GP point should be placed in the root canal(s) to maintain its patency during the external repair. Once the external repair has been completed, the tooth may be root treated. Internal repair is indicated when ECR is close to or has perforated the root canal system, and a surgical approach is not possible due to poor accessibility, or if surgical access will lead to an excessive amount of sound, tooth structure removal and/or the portal of entry cannot be located. RCT is completed, and the access cavity is restored together with the resorptive defect. Long shank burs and ultrasonic tips are useful in removing the resorptive lesion under a dental operating microscope. Biodentine may be used to repair resorbed dentine, and its high pH may help to arrest the osteoclastic action of any residual osteoclastic remnants.

Intentional replantation has been described in several case reports to successfully repair ECR defects. This treatment option is indicated when ECR cannot be accessed and repaired by an external or internal approach, for example, ECR located interproximally in the middle or apical third of the root.

For untreatable ECR, if asymptomatic, the patient may choose to review the tooth periodically to monitor for any progression of the ECR and/or the development of symptoms.

Extraction is the treatment option for unrestorable, symptomatic ECR lesions. ECR tends to predispose the affected tooth to fracture during extraction due to the

weakened and cavitated tooth structure and the infiltration of bone-like tissue in the resorptive cavity, and therefore, this needs to be carefully considered when ECR affects teeth in the aesthetic zone, a multidisciplinary approach is recommended.

External inflammatory resorption (EIR)

External inflammatory resorption (EIR) is present on the external surface of the root of majority of the teeth diagnosed with chronic apical periodontitis. EIR also affects teeth that suffer severe dental traumatic injury (for example, avulsion and luxation). In dental trauma injury (DTI) cases, EIR occurs as a result of injury to the root surface and adjacent periodontium. It is initially self-limiting and only focussed on the damaged root surface. Consequently, the loss of pulp vitality and infection of the necrotic pulp can result in the progression of EIR.

Clinical features

The clinical features of EIR are irreversible pulpitis and/or apical periodontitis such as pain, swelling, tenderness to percussion or palpation, sinus tract and discolouration. The affected tooth usually has a negative response to pulp sensitivity test.

Radiographic features

The diagnosis of EIR is confirmed on radiographic findings. EIR due to solely infected necrotic pulp contents may appear to be shorter or stunted in appearance than normally expected and sometimes have a ragged margin at the root end and associated with periapical radiolucency adjacent to the affected root. The root end may also have a ragged appearance. EIR associated with a history of moderate to severe DTI will usually have ragged bowl-shaped indentation along the lateral border of root surface with an adjacent periradicular radiolucency. Loss of lamina dura can also be seen in the region affected by the EIR and may be detected as early as 3–4 weeks after DTI. The root canal outline should be intact in the earlier stage of EIR.

Perforation of the root canal wall can occur in advanced stages where the EIR is diagnosed and treated late. EIR may be aggressive in nature, and the progression of the root resorption can be rapid after onset, for example, resorption of an entire root can occur within months. Therefore, it is essential to manage EIR as soon as possible and carry out RCT to arrest the progression of the resorption.

Management

The objective in the management of EIR cases is the disinfection to eliminate the aetiological factor, therefore RCT for the treatable cases and extraction for the unsalvageable cases. Root canal treatment will eliminate the stimulating factors (microbes and their toxins) and arrest the resorptive process, thus preventing further damage on the root, at the same time allowing hard tissue repair of the damaged root surface. When EIR is associated with DTI it is important to commence RCT as soon as possible due to the potentially rapidly progressing nature of EIR. Failure to do so may result in the affected tooth being extracted due to a severely resorbed root surface that is not possible to repair. Inadvertent overextrusion of the root filling is possible, therefore great care must be taken to ensure there is a good cone fit if gutta-percha is being used. Root filling with calcium silicate bioactive cements may be beneficial, due to their excellent biocompatibility.

External replacement resorption (ERR)

ERR refers to the resorption on the root surface and subsequent replacement by bone tissue, which may result in ankylosis. ERR is associated with severe luxation such as intrusion and avulsion injuries.

Clinical features

Clinical features of ERR include a lack of physiological mobility. The tooth may also be infraoccluded if ERR occurs in developing dentition.

Radiographic features

Conventional radiographic examination will reveal the absence of periodontal ligament space where the resorbed root surface appears to fuse with the surrounding bone. The root dentine will have an irregular or 'moth-eaten' appearance as the dentine is replaced by bone. Radiographs will only reveal the extent of ERR on the proximal aspects of the root.

Management

Presently, there is no treatment to arrest ERR. It may be self-limiting or continue to resorb the root and

replace it with bone-like tissue for years, eventually resorbing the entire root. In the older patient, the progression of ERR may be slow, and the tooth can remain functional for many years without the need for any active intervention.

The early detection and management of ERR and ankylosis are crucial in children and adolescents before or during their pubertal growth spurt. This is because ankylosed teeth will arrest the development of the alveolar ridge on that region whilst the adjacent alveolar ridge continues to grow, causing the affected tooth to become infraoccluded and the alveolar ridge to underdeveloped. This will compromise the aesthetics, phonetics, function of the patient and further complicate future restorative or prosthetic treatment.

It has also been advocated that ankylosed, infraoccluded tooth is intentionally decoronated below the level of cemento-enamel junction in children and adolescents. In this technique, a mucoperiosteal flap is raised, and the tooth is decoronated to 2 mm below the marginal bone level, the decoronated root is allowed to fill with a blood clot and sealed with the mucoperiosteal flap. This allows the root to be covered with attached mucosa. The decoronation aims to preserve the buccal-palatal dimension of the alveolar ridge, to allow for vertical growth and facilitate new bone formation above the decoronated root. Once the patient is an adult, in their early 20's, permanent restorative treatment such as dental implant treatment may be considered.

Extraction of the tooth with ERR is indicated if a pathological root fracture occurs or is likely to occur. It is also indicated in extremely compromised aesthetics. Extraction of an ankylosed tooth often requires a surgical approach and can result in a considerable amount of bone loss, complicating future implant placement.

The diagnosis and/or management of root resorption can be challenging for clinicians resulting in misdiagnosis. The importance of a thorough and systematic clinical and radiographic examination is paramount to ensure appropriate management. The prognosis of root resorption is dependent on an accurate and early diagnosis. Increasingly, CBCT is being used to confirm the diagnosis and/or aid management.